

NAVIGATING WASTE MANAGEMENT PRACTICES IN ISLAMIC PERSPECTIVE AMONG PUBLIC VENDORS IN JOLO MARKET

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ABSTRACT

The research study was conducted to navigate the waste management practices in accordance with Islamic point of view among public vendors in Jolo Market. A qualitative, descriptive research design was employed in this study. A total of 30 respondents were taken from public vendors in the Jolo Market. A survey interview was discussed with the vendors. Thematic analysis on the responses were utilized. The results of the study revealed that majority of public vendors in Jolo Market were unaware of the proper segregation of biodegradable and non-biodegradable garbage. Furthermore, the findings also revealed the lack of equipment for disposal of wastes and the proper management within the area needs improvement. Moreover, aside from behavioral aspects, public vendors are unaware that waste management is considered to be a religious obligation. Hence, there is a need for mass orientation.

Keywords: *Islamic Perspective, Jolo Market, Public Vendors, Waste Management Practices*

INTRODUCTION

Waste management is crucial for maintaining a clean and healthy environment. According to Rahman N. Protecting and conserving the environment is the responsibility of every individual including religious people in the Islamic context. Religious people play an

important role in environmental conservation because they have the ability to cultivate public awareness on environmental conservation by linking the field of environmental conservation with religious knowledge (Rahman, 2021).

According to Muslim scholars, the universe is governed and regulated by the principles of unity, balance, and harmony that characterise the interactive unifying principle -tawhid. The Qur'an repeatedly quotes that the universe is characterised by proportion, harmony, and beauty, which are the hallmarks of Divine craftsmanship (Sanjotis, 2012).

Sanjotis further cited Idris 1990 and Khalid et.al 1992 that the second concept of Islamic environmental ethics is stewardship "khilafah". He stressed, The Qur'an declares that human beings are stewards of Allah's creation "Behold, the Lord said to the angels: "I will create a vicegerent on earth" (Qur'an 2:30). Furthermore, human beings need to refrain from mischief (actions leading to the corruption of the environment) (Sanjotis, 2012).

Hence, incorporating Islamic perspective in waste management is important because Islam emphasizes the importance of caring for the environment and being responsible stewards of the earth. Additionally, the teachings of Islam regarding environmental stewardship, cleanliness, and waste management explores concepts such as "mizan" (balance), "amanah" (trust), and "khilafah" (stewardship), which emphasize the responsibility of Muslims to protect and preserve the environment.

The Qur'an and Hadiths contain numerous teachings that emphasize the importance of cleanliness, conservation and sustainability. By incorporating Islamic principles into waste management practices, individuals and communities can align their religious beliefs and contribute to a more sustainable and environmentally-friendly society. As stated by Mariyam, Cochrane, Zuhara, & McKay, (2022) a study conducted a survey targeting Muslim consumers in a university in Qatar and found that there is a sense of ethical consumption behavior. The Islamic philosophy of moderation or "wastiya" encourages sharing resources rather than unnecessary wastage based on the Quranic quote [7:31], "Eat and drink but waste not by excess; Verily Allah loves not the excessive", which teaches Muslims to take heed of careless consumption.

The issue of protecting human health and the environment is the responsibility of the state and the experts, but it is evident that this problem is part of the teaching in Islam...An important point that needs to be underlined is that Islam prioritizes health, self, and the environment. This is very important because all the activities we do will run optimally if we are physically, spiritually, and mentally healthy. Likewise, without a healthy environment, it will hurt the Muslim community itself.

Therefore, Islam invites its people to maintain the health of both humans and their environment in every religious message (Mishbahuddin, et.al., 2021)

Furthermore, Incorporating Islamic principles in public awareness campaigns can effectively promote proper solid waste management behavior among Muslims. Studies

have shown that using Islamic education channels and expressions to address environmental issues has positive effects in raising awareness (Ismail, 2016).

Research Questions

This research aims to answer the following questions:

1. What are the Islamic perspectives on waste management among public vendors in Jolo?
2. What are the waste management practices of public vendors in Jolo market?
3. What challenges do public vendors face in implementing waste management practices in line with Islamic principles in Jolo market?
4. Does the Islamic perspective of waste management influence the waste management practices of public vendors in Jolo market?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design	: Descriptive research design, qualitative approach.
Research Locale	: Jolo Public Market in Serantes St., Walled City, Jolo, Sulu.
Respondents	: 30 vendors selected through random sampling.
Data Collection	: Survey questionnaire used to gather data on waste management practices.
Data Analysis:	Thematic analysis employed to analyze qualitative responses.

RESULTS

The results obtained from the survey shed light on the pressing issue of waste management within the study area. The majority of the respondents expressed their concerns and shared their insights regarding waste management practices, to wit:

Ignorance

A significant finding from the survey is that the respondents tend to dispose of their waste in a single container, without segregating biodegradable and non-biodegradable waste. This practice highlights a lack of awareness and adherence to proper waste disposal methods. It is imperative to know how waste properly disposed in order to attain the healthier and safe lifestyle.

Recognizing the difference between these types of waste is essential for effective recycling and waste management. It informs which materials can be safely composted, and which require recycling or special disposal methods to mitigate their environmental impact. Biodegradable waste comprises materials that decompose naturally under the action of microorganisms such as bacteria and fungi. This includes kitchen waste, garden waste, paper, and wood. In contrast, non-biodegradable waste consists of materials that

cannot be easily broken down by natural processes. This includes plastics, metals, glass, and certain types of chemicals (Rodrigues, 2024).

Lack of Tools Necessary for Waste Disposal

One crucial aspect that emerged from the respondents' feedback is the absence of suitable waste disposal systems and containers. Despite acknowledging the importance of proper waste disposal, the respondents face challenges in implementing it due to a lack of equipment. They expressed a need for composting facilities and the ability to determine whether their waste can be composted or not. Furthermore, the infrequency of garbage collection forces them to store their waste, leading to adverse consequences.

Proper Management

The accumulation of waste within the Jolo market area has resulted from these inadequate waste management practices. The presence of dirt and foul odors has not only compromised the aesthetic appeal of the area but has also had a detrimental impact on the quality of their products and the health of the community members.

Moreover, it was observed that some individuals resort to haphazard waste disposal methods, such as discarding waste in creeks or canals, further exacerbating the environmental degradation. Others opt to pile up waste in various locations, compounding the waste management challenges faced by the community.

It is inseparable from the problems faced, one of which is the cleanliness of market stalls and the health of the market environment. The problem of stall cleanliness and the health of the market environment tends to increase if it does not get special attention and high concern from the kiosk owner traders and market environmental cleaners. A good and correct waste management system will provide the advantage of reducing pollution caused by the accumulation of waste, by providing alternative efforts due to the generation of well-managed waste (Ariani, 2021).

Healthy, clean and comfortable environment also expected to exist a market, as well as traditional market. The goods in traditional market usually household daily needs... Creating a clean and healthy environment is a shared responsibility. Especially the people around the neighborhood. They have an important role in protecting the environment and creating a clean and healthy environment. Creating a clean and healthy environment in the market is a shared responsibility of all stakeholder (P.M.H., 2018).

Behavioral Aspects

Additionally, the findings highlight the importance of understanding local contexts and perceptions when developing waste management strategies. To align with the cultural and religious values of the target community that can increase their relevance and effectiveness. By leveraging the moral and spiritual dimensions of waste management found in Islamic teachings, future initiatives may be better positioned to drive behavioral

change and foster a sense of environmental stewardship among the public vendors in the Jolo market.

Moreover, it was stressed in a study that components of environmental awareness can be classified into two aspects: perception and behaviour, that is, the perception of environmental problems and the behavioural inclination to protect the environment. The perception of environmental problems involves people's objective knowledge, perception and environmental realities (Desa, Kadir, & Yusooff, (2011).

DISCUSSION

Both the literature and the study emphasize the importance of proper waste management practices in maintaining environmental health and cleanliness. The Islamic perspective on waste management, as discussed in the literature, aligns with the need for responsible waste disposal highlighted in the study findings. Both sources underscore the significance of avoiding wasteful behaviors, such as indiscriminate waste disposal and improper handling of resources.

The literature highlights Islamic teaching on environmental stewardship and waste management, while the study findings reveal a lack of awareness among public vendors in the Jolo market regarding the religious significance of waste management. While the literature discusses the rewards and prohibitions related to waste management in Islam, the study findings point out specific challenges faced by public vendors, such as the lack of necessary equipment and infrastructure for effective waste disposal.

The study extends the existing literature by providing insights into the practical challenges and perceptions of waste management among public vendors in specific market setting. By uncovering the gap in understanding Islamic teachings on waste management among vendors, the study contributes to the discourse on integrating religious principles into environmental practices.

The comparison highlights the needs for educational efforts to bridge the gap between Islamic teachings on waste management and the awareness of public vendors in the Jolo market. Understanding the divergence between literature and study findings underscores the importance of context-specific waste management strategies aligned with cultural and religious values. By comparing the literature with the study findings, it becomes evident that while the theoretical framework of Islamic waste management is well –established, practical implementation and awareness among public vendors present significant challenges that require targeted interventions and educational initiatives.

Conclusions

The importance of raising awareness about proper waste management practices and integrating Islamic teachings on cleanliness and resource conservation. By addressing

the gaps in knowledge and behavior, and leveraging religious values, initiatives can be tailored to promote sustainable waste management practices and foster a sense of environmental responsibility among public vendors in the Jolo market.

Recommendations

To address the challenges in waste management practices at Jolo market, several strategies can be implemented. Here are some recommendations for improving waste management in the market:

1. **Public Awareness Campaigns:** conducting educational programs and awareness campaigns to inform vendors, customers and the local community about the importance of proper waste disposal and recycling practices;
 2. **Infrastructure Improvement:** investing in waste segregation bins, recycling facilities, and proper waste disposal infrastructure within the market area to encourage proper waste management;
 3. **Regular Waste Collection:** establish a regular waste collection schedule to ensure that waste is collected and disposed of in a timely manner to prevent accumulation and littering;
 4. **Collaboration with Local Authorities:** working closely with local government authorities to enforce waste management regulations, conduct inspections and implement penalties for non-compliance with waste disposal guidelines;
 5. **Promoting Sustainable Practices:** encouraging the use of eco-friendly packaging materials, reusable containers and promoting sustainable practices among vendors and customers to reduce waste generation;
 6. **Community Engagement:** involving the local community in waste management initiatives through volunteer clean-up drives, recycling programs, and community participation in keeping the market clean;
 7. **Monitoring and Evaluation:** implementing a monitoring and evaluation system to track progress, measure the effectiveness of waste management initiatives, and make necessary adjustments to improve efficiency.
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Compliance with Ethical Standards

In order to ensure informed consent, the researchers emphasized the importance of the respondents' understanding and willingness to participate in the study. Detailed information and assurances were provided to ensure that the respondents were fully informed and had the freedom to choose whether or not to participate. The researchers also guaranteed the confidentiality of any information shared, reassuring the respondents that their privacy would be protected and their responses would remain confidential.

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